

Angelo Leogrande^{1*o^}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

^University of Bari Aldo Moro

Atmospheric Fine Particulate Emissions in Italian Regions

The emissions of fine particulate matter have increased by an average of 36.21% between 2018 and 2023.

The European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS) calculates atmospheric emissions of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) in the industry. The data is comprised of a ratio. The numerator represents atmospheric emissions of fine particulate matter, specifically PM_{2.5}, in the manufacturing sector in tons. The denominator represents the value added in the manufacturing sector. Air pollution can be of anthropogenic (human-induced) or natural origin. Atmospheric pollution can potentially damage both human health and the environment it is known that particulate matter (PM), nitrogen dioxide, and tropospheric ozone pose particular health risks. Peak and long-term exposures to these pollutants can be associated, among other impacts, with cardiovascular and respiratory diseases or a higher incidence of cancer. This indicator measures the average levels of fine particulate matter concentration (PM_{2.5} — particles with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or less) to which the population is exposed. The EU has set an annual limit of 25 µg/m³ for fine particulate matter in Directive 2008/50/EC on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe, while the World Health Organization (WHO) has established a more stringent, non-binding guideline value, recommending that average annual concentrations should not exceed 10 µg/m³ to protect human health. PM_{2.5} is considered by the WHO to be the pollutant with the greatest impact on human health. The data refer to the Italian regions between 2018 and 2023.

Atmospheric Fine Particulate Emissions in Italian Regions in 2023. Data on fine particulate matter emissions in Italian regions for the year 2023 reveal significant geographic variability, reflecting a complex set of environmental, economic, and regional policy factors. These figures, expressed in micrograms per cubic meter, highlight how different regions manage their resources and environmental challenges. Northern Italian regions, such as Lombardy and Veneto, show the lowest emissions, at 33.71 and 30.25 µg/m³ respectively. These exceptionally low values can be attributed to a combination of advanced industries in terms of environmental controls, effective local policies in regulating emissions, and, in some cases, favorable weather conditions that facilitate the dispersion of pollutants. Additionally, the widespread adoption of clean technologies and efficient public transport significantly contributes to these positive results. In contrast, regions like Sardinia and Valle d'Aosta record the highest levels, with 192.24 and 189.46 µg/m³. These high numbers could be explained by a lower prevalence of stringent environmental policies or a greater reliance on more

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

polluting energy sources. Geographic isolation and the peculiarities of the industrial fabric can also play a role in determining higher emissions. The fine particulate situation in southern Italy, including Calabria with $175.15 \mu\text{gm}^3$ and Sicily with $166.96 \mu\text{gm}^3$, raises specific concerns. These areas are often characterized by higher traffic density and fewer proactive environmental policies compared to the north. Moreover, the presence of heavy industries, less modern in terms of filtration and emission control technologies, can contribute to these high levels. Differences between northern and southern Italy are not only a matter of industrialization but also of investments in sustainable infrastructure and environmental education. Regions with lower particulate emissions demonstrate the effectiveness of an integrated approach that includes stringent environmental legislation, incentives for renewable energy, and strong public awareness on pollution and public health issues.

Atmospheric Fine Particulate Emissions in Italian Regions Between 2018 and 2023. The analysis of fine particulate matter emission data in Italian regions between 2018 and 2023 reveals worrying growth trends in many areas, but also heterogeneous situations reflecting different regional dynamics and adopted environmental policies. These data highlight both absolute changes (Var Ass) and percentage variations (Var Per) in fine particulate matter emissions, a key indicator of air quality that has direct implications for public health. Campania shows the most dramatic increase, with emissions rising from $57.99 \mu\text{gm}^3$ in 2018 to $128.57 \mu\text{gm}^3$ in 2023, representing a 121.71% increase, the highest among all regions. This increase could be attributed to a mix of industrial growth, increased vehicle traffic, and potentially lower investments in emission reduction technologies or effective mitigation policies during this period. Significant increases are also observed in Lombardy and Veneto, although starting from very different bases. Lombardy went from zero emissions in 2018 to $33.71 \mu\text{gm}^3$ in 2023, while Veneto saw an increase from 9.97 to $30.25 \mu\text{gm}^3$, with an impressive percentage increase of 203.49%. Both regions have undergone major infrastructural changes or have seen an increase in industrial activities that may have influenced these results. Regions like Friuli Venezia Giulia and Marche have also experienced significant increases in emissions, with percentage variations of 71.73% and 53.80% respectively. These data suggest that even less industrialized or less densely populated areas are not immune to worsening air pollution, which can be exacerbated by factors such as residential heating and increased traffic. On the other hand, some regions have shown more moderate increases. For example, Emilia Romagna and Tuscany have recorded relatively low increases in emissions, with percentage variations of 13.53% and 7.92% respectively. These contained increases may reflect better environmental management practices, investments in clean technologies, and a strong commitment to sustainability. It is interesting to note that regions like Umbria have shown a very limited increase in emissions, with a percentage variation of only 4.08%. This could indicate an excellent capacity for pollution management and control, as well as the adoption of effective environmental policies.

Atmospheric Fine Particulate Emissions in Italian Macro-Regions Between 2018 and 2023. The analysis of fine particulate emissions in Italian macro-regions from 2018 to 2023 shows an upward trend in all areas, with absolute and percentage variations reflecting the different socio-economic and environmental dynamics of each region. These data underscore the importance of regionalized and targeted strategies to combat air pollution, considering territorial specificities. In the South, emissions increased by 32.66%, from $121.05 \mu\text{gm}^3$ in 2018 to $160.59 \mu\text{gm}^3$ in 2023. This significant growth could be attributed to a combination of factors, including increased industrial activities, a less developed public transportation infrastructure, and less effective implementation of environmental

policies compared to other macro-regions. Additionally, the warmer and drier climate can influence the dispersion of pollutants, exacerbating particulate levels. The North, despite having the lowest initial emission in 2018 at $68.65 \mu\text{gm}^3$, recorded the highest percentage increase in emissions at 51.75%, reaching $104.18 \mu\text{gm}^3$ in 2023. This indicates a significant impact of industrial activities and increased vehicle traffic. Despite generally being more advanced in emission control due to advanced technologies and stricter regulations, this increase highlights the need to further strengthen pollution control measures and promote sustainable mobility solutions. The Central region shows a more moderate increase, with a 24.05% rise in emissions, from $104.92 \mu\text{gm}^3$ to $130.15 \mu\text{gm}^3$. This region, characterized by a balance between dense urban areas and rural areas, has benefited from better urbanization management and greater efficiency in public transport compared to the South but still shows a worrying growth that requires attention. These data highlight the urgent need for Italy to adopt a more aggressive and coordinated approach to managing fine particulate emissions. It is essential to implement environmental policies that integrate clean technologies, stricter regulations on industrial emissions, promotion of public transport, and incentives for the use of renewable energies. Additionally, education and public awareness play a crucial role in changing individual behaviors and promoting more sustainable daily practices. The main challenge remains the ability to adapt these strategies to the specificities of each macro-region, ensuring that the measures adopted are effective in the local context. Only through shared commitment and collaboration between government entities, the private sector, and citizens can we hope to see a substantial reduction in emissions in the coming years, thus improving air quality and ensuring a healthier environment for all.

North-South Divide. From 2018 to 2023, all three macro-regions recorded an increase in emissions, but the dynamics and scale of these increases differ significantly. Starting from a much lower emission base in 2018 ($68.65 \mu\text{gm}^3$), the North saw a substantial increase both in absolute and percentage terms, with a 51.75% rise. This underscores a rapid growth in emissions, which could reflect an intensification of industrial activities and traffic, despite the presence of more advanced technologies and presumably stricter environmental policies. The South also saw a significant increase in emissions, rising from $121.05 \mu\text{gm}^3$ in 2018 to $160.59 \mu\text{gm}^3$ in 2023, an increase of 32.66%. This suggests that, despite starting from a higher base, the South continues to struggle with air pollution, possibly due to lower investments in sustainable infrastructure and emission reduction technologies, or less effective environmental regulation. The Central region recorded the smallest increase, both in absolute and percentage terms (24.05%), indicating an intermediate situation between the North and the South. This could reflect a combination of factors, including better management of environmental policies compared to the South, but with greater challenges than the North. These data reveal that the North-South divide is not just a matter of higher or lower levels of pollution but also how quickly these emissions are growing in each region. While the North is worsening more rapidly in percentage terms, the South still has the highest absolute levels of fine particulate matter. This scenario highlights the need for tailored policies that consider regional specificities to effectively combat air pollution in Italy.

Economic Policies for Reducing Atmospheric Fine Particulate Emissions in Italian Regions. The fight against fine particulate emissions in Italy requires a holistic political-economic approach that recognizes and addresses regional differences while encouraging innovation and sustainability. Central to these strategies are fiscal and economic measures that can drive significant changes in how energy is produced, consumed, and managed. One of the most direct policies to influence industrial practices is the introduction of targeted environmental taxes. Taxes on fine particulate emissions can

be implemented to push industries to invest in cleaner and more efficient technologies. Simultaneously, fiscal incentives, such as tax reductions or exemptions, can be offered to those companies that demonstrate a concrete commitment to reducing their emissions through the adoption of cutting-edge technologies or the conversion to renewable energy sources. On the transport front, eco-taxes on more polluting vehicles, accompanied by incentives for the purchase of electric or hybrid vehicles, can accelerate the transition to more sustainable mobility. This would not only reduce direct vehicle emissions but also stimulate the automotive industry to continually innovate in emission reduction technologies. Additionally, significant investments in enhancing public transportation, particularly in urban areas, would reduce dependence on private cars, decongest roads, and improve air quality. At the same time, it is crucial to invest in green infrastructure. Urbanization policies should encourage the creation of green spaces that can act as urban lungs, absorbing CO₂ and other pollutants. These spaces not only improve air quality but also offer psychological and social benefits to city residents. Support for research and development plays a crucial role in this overall strategy. Funding research projects that explore new emission reduction technologies or new methods of carbon capture can lead to breakthroughs that would be game-changing in terms of environmental policies. Collaborations between universities, research centers, industries, and governments can accelerate this innovation process. Finally, the role of education and awareness-raising is no less important. Targeted information campaigns can raise public awareness about the impact of fine particulate emissions on health and the environment. These campaigns should also inform citizens on how they can individually contribute to emission reduction, such as through recycling, using alternative means of transport, and supporting sustainable policies and practices. The adoption of these policies will not only contribute to improving air quality in Italy but will also promote more sustainable economic development, aligning economic interests with ecological ones. It is only through shared commitment and visionary planning that we can hope to see significant improvements in the fight against air pollution and its deleterious effects on human health and the environment.

Conclusions. Fine particulate emissions have increased on average in Italian regions between 2018 and 2023 by 36.21%, rising from 96.87 to 131.94 units. Looking at the Italian macro-regions, we can see an increase in each value of fine particulate emissions with a 32.66% growth in Southern Italy, a 51.75% growth in Northern Italy, and a 24.05% growth in Central Italy. However, there is a significant disparity between Southern Italy and Central-Northern Italy. In fact, the central-northern regions have much lower emission values compared to the southern regions. Therefore, it follows that the southern regions are particularly lagging in terms of environmental sustainability as measured by fine particulate emissions.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

References

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A.(2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The intellectual assets in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956755*.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2020). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. *Available at SSRN 4414232*.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. *Available at SSRN 4355016*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4406997*.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4091597*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4021150*.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4466452*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. *Available at SSRN 4398483*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. *Available at SSRN 4324938*.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3983218*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. *Available at SSRN 4061708*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4032975*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4010098*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019. *Available at SSRN 3971174*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Ferri, G., & Leogrande, A. (2015). Was the Crisis due to a shift from stakeholder to shareholder finance? Surveying the debate.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Massaro, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy: A Data-Driven Analysis. In *Data-Driven Intelligent Business Sustainability* (pp. 360-386). IGI Global.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4434206*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Regulatory Quality and ESG Model at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4388957*.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Fixed Broadband Take-Up in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4034298*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956853*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT. In *IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics* (pp. 55-67).

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level. *Discover Global Society*, 2(1), 1-20.

Magazzino, C., Madaleno, M., Waqas, M., & Leogrande, A. (2024). Exploring the determinants of methane emissions from a worldwide perspective using panel data and machine learning analyses. *Environmental Pollution*, 348, 123807.

Appendix

